

**FROM THE PROCESS OF ESTABLISHING "NEW UZBEKISTAN"
ARRAYS IN SURKHONDARYO REGION**

Abduraimov, son of Fazliddin Shamsiddin

Independent researcher of Termiz State University

ORCID ID: 0009-0007-1024-1325

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Abstract: The construction industry is one of the "drivers" of our national economy. In recent years, there has been a sharp increase in the construction sector of our country. The expansion of the construction industry is directly related to factors such as population growth, population welfare and purchasing power. In turn, the development of the construction industry will help create additional jobs and improve infrastructure. The article talks about the process of building "New Uzbekistan" massifs in Surkhondaryo region.

Key words: construction, "New Uzbekistan" massifs, Saryosiy, Boysun, Jarkorgon and Angor.

Аннотация: Строительная отрасль является одним из «драйверов» нашей национальной экономики. В последние годы наблюдается резкий рост строительного сектора нашей страны. Расширение строительной отрасли напрямую связано с такими факторами, как рост населения, благосостояние населения и покупательная способность. В свою очередь, развитие строительной отрасли будет способствовать созданию дополнительных рабочих мест и улучшению инфраструктуры. В статье рассказывается о процессе строительства массивов «Новый Узбекистан» в Сурхандарьинской области.

Ключевые слова: строительство, массивы «Новый Узбекистан», Сарыосий, Байсун, Жаркоргон и Ангор.

"New Uzbekistan" massifs are being built in Surkhondaryo region in 2022. "New Uzbekistan" massifs with 1,600 apartments were built in Sariosia, Boysun, Jarkorgon and Angor districts of Surkhondaryo region. Special attention was paid to the quality, price and construction culture of the multi-storey buildings under construction, and a school, pre-school education, polyclinic buildings and necessary infrastructure facilities were also built in each massif. The new educational building of Termiz State University was commissioned. A new modern building with 1,850 seats with all conditions was put into use for the Faculty of Information Technologies of Termiz State University. University luminaries, poets, artists, professors, teachers, and students took part in the solemn ceremony held on this occasion. The 7-story building has all the facilities for students, including 51 lecture halls, 8 computer rooms, a library with more

than seven thousand scientific and artistic books, three lecture halls with a capacity of 100 students each, 1 council hall, 9 a laboratory, a department and an administration room were built. All computers are connected to the Internet, Wi-Fi zones are established. Wide and bright auditoriums are equipped with a smart board. 176 professors and staff work in the new educational building, which can accommodate 1,850 students at a time. In 2020-2022, 421 apartment buildings with 15,466 apartments with an area of 866,000 square meters were built in Surkhandarya region. Until recently, there were mainly 2- and 4-story houses in the region, but in 2021, 7-, 9-, and 10-story houses were built, and from 2022, 12-, 14-, and 16-story houses were built.

In 2022, investments in the amount of 653 million US dollars were attracted in the field of construction and industrial products production in the oasis. From this:

- the volume of foreign direct investments is 245 million US dollars;
- production volume reached 600 billion soums. Including:
- Cement - 1.9 million tons;
- Construction window - 30 thousand square meters;
- Plasterboard - 6 million square meters;
- Dry mixtures - 11 thousand tons;
- Ceramic tile - 100,000 square meters;
- Aerated concrete - 2.4 thousand cubic meters of construction and industrial products were produced. — Infographics (https://t.me/surxonstat_uz/11093)

Information about the construction works performed in Surkhandarya region in January-November 2022. Construction works worth 5 trillion 816 billion 114 million soums were performed by 3,021 construction enterprises in the region during January-November 2022. Construction works were carried out by 15 large construction organizations, 3,006 small enterprises and micro-firms. In 2022, new housing units worth 1 trillion 161 billion 405 million soums were built, and 198 billion 298 million soums were spent on housing repairs. Regions with a high share of construction works: — Termiz city; — Sariosia district; — Denov district; - Jarkurgan district.

Student housing of the Bakhchik school in Termiz city was handed over in January 2023. The dormitory of the Republican boarding school specialized in the art of bacchanalian art in the city of Termiz has 150 beds and consists of 4 floors. Built by the Railwaymen in a fully equipped state, this dormitory has a library, kitchen, gym, classroom, spiritual room, laundry and drying rooms and

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dormitories. During the President's visit to our region on June 1-2, 2021, the proposal of Abdurahman Abdinazarov, a young Bakhshi from Kiziri, to build a modern dormitory for the Bakhshi school was supported, and the foundation for its construction was laid in December of the same year. In Surkhandarya region, in 2022, agricultural products were grown on 57,500 hectares, including 40,000 hectares of vegetables and 17,500 hectares of sugarcane. According to the results of the 9th month of 2022, 1 million 750,000 tons of crops were harvested. 14 processing enterprises have been established in the oasis, their annual capacity is 158.3 thousand tons. In addition, in order to create a food reserve for the winter and spring seasons, 167 processing enterprises collected 18,100 tons of potatoes, 3,300 tons of onions, 9,300 tons of carrots, and 3,300 tons of rice products. . 132 refrigerators and 31 ordinary warehouses with a capacity of 88,360 tons have been involved in stockpiling and storage. The level of provision of centralized drinking water to the residents of Surkhandarya region is increasing. As of January 2023, the population of the republic is provided with centralized drinking water at 74.4 percent (<https://t.me/uzsuv/8993>). This indicator is planned to reach 87% by 2026 in accordance with the Development Strategy. Today, the level of provision of centralized drinking water for the population of Surkhandarya region is 60.8 percent. Entrepreneurs in connection with the requirements of Decree No. PF-220 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan of September 9, 2022 regarding the wider use of renewable energy sources by the population and business entities and attracting private investments in the construction of micro and small hydroelectric power stations in the Regional General Directorate of Construction in cooperation with JSC "Uzbekgidroenergo" and the regional administration and a "Roadshow" (presentation) was held for investors. The representatives of Uzbekgidroenergo JSC introduced the projects planned to be implemented on the construction of micro and small hydroelectric power plants in the region to the deputy governors, heads of organizations and enterprises related to the issue, and entrepreneurs. Insights into the effective use of relevant legal privileges were given in this direction.

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